

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARY MONETTE W. DIPUTADO, CHRA, DBA

Assistant Professor I

Negros Oriental State University

mwee423@gmail.com

“MY PERFECT DOG”

My dog's the fattest dog in all the lands
My biscuits loosely held in my two hands
Unsuspecting chicken on tabletops
None are safe from the dog who eats nonstop

My dog's the angriest dog in this world
All morning and evening - it bark, bark, barked
Too little attention, it's more barking
Too much attention, it's more snarling

My dog is the silliest dog on Earth
He plays dead tongue-out for all it is worth
He zooms around the room like a missile
All that weight, yet he's quick as a whistle

My dog's fat, and angry, and so silly
My perfect dog and I love him truly